

Barriers and Drivers to the Adoption of Artificial Intelligence in Digital Marketing By Indian Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMES)

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Abstract :- In India, where there is a fast-paced economic growth, Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) are the backbone of the growth and development in the country. Their adoption of revolutionary technologies, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), is, nevertheless, a complex issue that should be explored in detail. This study investigates the many variables that determine the intention of Indian MSMEs to adopt AI-driven digital marketing solutions.

It is based on an enhanced Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and presents and empirically confirms a holistic model in which Perceived Usefulness and Perceived Ease of Use are the main predictors of adoption intention, and are influenced by unique organizational and environmental conditions.

A quantitative survey was done on 278 MSME owner-managers in India and the analysis was done with Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) methods. The study results have shown that Perceived Usefulness comes out as the most important predictor of adoption intention. Competitive Pressure significantly enhances the Perceived Ease of Use, suggesting market urgency lowers adoption barriers. Moreover, Vendor Support is a critical factor in driving Perceived Usefulness by ensuring organizations can extract value from the tools.

The study will add to the more advanced comprehension of the adoption decision-making process among MSMEs and will offer useful suggestions to the technology vendors and policymakers to facilitate the perception value and availability of AI tools to these vital business

entities.

Keywords :- Artificial Intelligence (AI), Marketing Technology, Technology Adoption, MSMEs, India, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

1. Introduction :- The MSMEs have provided the Indian economy with the backbone in terms of innovation, creation of employment and local entrepreneurship. With the arrival of Artificial Intelligence, these companies find themselves in an inflection point as India gets integrated into the digital economy. AI ceases to exist as a mere theory but is an established business instrument that can enhance the performance of firms and competitive advantage. In the case of MSMEs, AI is a strategic chance to be in competition with more prominent companies by improving decision-making, customer interaction, and efficiency of the work. However, the penetration of AI among Indian MSMEs is still low, even though it has the potential. Although large organisations have already embraced AI into their basic operations, the majority of MSMEs remain at the backyard and they are limited by organisational, structural and perceptual factors.

Such discrepancy between potential and practice poses significant questions of what influences AI adoption decisions. The technical problem is not the only difficulty but the strategic preparedness and the opinion of the managers. Previous studies indicate that MSMEs have continued to remain resistant to the adoption of hi-tech digital systems, and AI further complicates the decision to adopt systems. To fill this gap, the

current study will focus on the factors that determine the adoption of AI by Indian MSMEs in particular, the AI-based marketing tools that have direct impact on customer interaction, sales optimisation and long-term growth. Based on the Technology Acceptance Model, the research problem is the effect of the perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on managerial intentions and the impact of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use contingent on organisational constraints and external pressures. The results are intended to offer practical implications on the managers of MSMEs, technology suppliers, and policy-makers who are interested in speeding up the process of AI-based change in the Indian economic mainframe.

2. Review of Literature and The development of Hypotheses :-

In the business sector, especially in marketing, AI applications can be used to perform the automated analysis of data, individual communication, identification of leads, and uninterrupted customer support through tools like predictive analytics and chatbots (Kshetri et al., 2024; Morabi and Dass, 2022; Aljarboa, 2024). These applications are promising improvement in both operational performance and decision-making, as well as financial performance (Bhalla, 2025). Nevertheless, the implementation of AI is not that simple and risky. Poor quality of data, difficulties in system integration, and high technical complexity are the regular challenges in organisations that may bring implementation efforts to a screeching halt instead of being minor operational concerns (Jain et al., 2025; Bhalerao et al., 2022; Kar et al., 2021).

The structural constraints further affect these issues among MSMEs. Previous studies note that long-term technical, organisational, human, financial, and institutional obstacles influence the way managers perceived and adopted them. Low quality of digital infrastructure, lack of coordination in data and the absence of system compatibility decreases trust in AI solutions (Jain et al., 2025; Kar et al., 2021). Poor digital preparedness, vague strategies, and poor internal

coordination are the organisational barriers that degrade managerial faith in the successful implementation (Govori & Sejdija, 2023; Campion et al., 2022). The barriers posed by humans include the lack of skills, exposure to new technologies, and employee resistance due to work insecurity (Hansen and Bogh, 2021; Jadhav, 2021). Some perceived risk is added by financial constraints caused by expensive acquisition and maintenance and limited access to capital (Kulkarni et al., 2024; Rawashdeh, 2023). The adoption is further constrained by institutional factors, such as poor vendor support, data security concerns, regulatory uncertainty, and low trust towards the AI systems (Wei and Pardo, 2022; Ade-Ibajola and Okonkwo, 2023; Beltempo et al., 2023). These barriers have a direct effect on the perception of usefulness and perceived ease of use, and the conclusion is that there is a need to expand classic TAM-based explanations into the MSME environment.

2.1. Research Objectives :-

- To test how the Perceived Ease of Use and Perceived Usefulness affect the Intention to Adopt AI marketing tools among Indian MSMEs.
- To examine the effect of Competitive Pressure on the felt Ease of Use of AI marketing technologies.
- To determine whether Vendor Support plays a role in the enhancement of the Perceived Usefulness of AI marketing solutions.
- To examine the influence of Financial Resources and Employee Technical Skills on the adoption process.
- To identify and measure key organizational, technical, human and external barriers affecting AI adoption among MSMEs.

2.2. Research Hypotheses :-

- H1: Perceived Ease of Use positively influences Perceived Usefulness.
- H2: Perceived Ease of Use positively influences Intention to Adopt AI.
- H3: Perceived Usefulness positively influences Intention to Adopt AI.
- H4: Competitive Pressure positively influences

Perceived Ease of Use.

- H5: Financial Resources positively influence Perceived Usefulness.
- H6: Vendor Support positively influences Perceived Usefulness.
- H7: Employee Technical Skills positively influence Perceived Ease of Use.

2.3. The Conceptual Framework: An Extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) :-

A scientific examination of the managerial decision making in technology adoption must have a model that would connect perceptions with behavioural intention. Technology Acceptance Model is the most popular model introduced by Davis in 1989 as the model is considered to be simple and has a great explanatory power.

This leads to our conceptual model, illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Conceptual Research Model :-

3. **Research Methodology :-** The study adopted a quantitative, cross-sectional research design. Data were collected through a structured online survey administered to Indian MSME owner-managers and senior executives. Stratified sampling was used based on MSMEs registered on the Udyam portal to ensure sectoral diversity. Power analysis indicated a minimum sample of 153 respondents, while 278 valid responses were retained after data screening.

The questionnaire measured seven latent constructs using items adapted from validated studies. All items were rated on seven-point Likert scales. Data analysis was conducted using SmartPLS 4.1 for PLS-SEM, supported by descriptive statistics generated in SPSS. The analysis followed a two-stage approach, assessing the measurement model followed by the structural model

Fig 2. SmartPLS

Result Results :-The measurement model demonstrated strong reliability and validity. All indicator loadings exceeded threshold values. Cronbach’s Alpha ranged from 0.808 to 0.932, Composite Reliability from 0.847 to 0.949, and AVE values exceeded 0.50 for all constructs in Table 1. Discriminant validity was confirmed using the Fornell–Larcker criterion.

Table :- Reliability and Validity

Construct	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha (α)	Composite Reliability (ρ_c)	AVE
Competitive Pressure (CP)	CP1-CP5	0.880 - 0.898	0.932	0.949	0.787
Employee Tech Skills (ETS)	ETS1-ETS3	0.895 - 0.907	0.886	0.929	0.814
Financial Resources (FR)	FR1-FR4	0.849 - 0.887	0.898	0.929	0.766
Intention to Adopt (IA)	IA1-IA5	0.703 - 0.800	0.809	0.867	0.566
Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU)	PEOU1-PEOU4	0.725 - 0.799	0.808	0.847	0.581
Perceived Usefulness (PU)	PU1-PU4	0.704 - 0.892	0.827	0.886	0.662
Vendor Support (VS)	VS1-VS4	0.840 - 0.896	0.886	0.921	0.745

Sourc :-

Results :- Structural model results in Table 2 indicate that Perceived Ease of Use significantly influences Perceived Usefulness and Intention to Adopt, while Perceived Usefulness strongly predicts adoption intention. Competitive Pressure significantly enhances Perceived Ease of Use, and Vendor Support positively influences Perceived Usefulness. Financial Resources and Employee Technical Skills did not exhibit significant effects.

Table 2: Structural Model Results (Hypothesis Testing)

Relationship (Path)	Path Coeff (β)	T Statistics	P Values	Result
H1: PEOU → PU	0.249	4.037	0.000	Supported
H2: PEOU → IA	0.408	9.023	0.000	Supported
H3: PU → IA	0.386	8.351	0.000	Supported

Tested Path: CP → PEOU	0.462	3.659	0.000	Significant
Tested Path: ETS → PU	0.156	1.442	0.149	Not Supported
Tested Path: FR → PEOU	-0.049	0.368	0.713	Not Supported
Tested Path: VS → PU	0.194	1.999	0.046	Supported

Sourc.

Results :- Descriptive analysis reveals high agreement on skill-related, financial, and security-related barriers, reinforcing the role of organisational and institutional constraints in AI adoption.

Structural Model Assessment :- Hypotheses were tested using bootstrapping (5,000 subsamples). The results in Table 2 show the path coefficients, t-statistics, and p-values.

5. Discussion :- The study validates the core relationships of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) within the context of AI marketing tool adoption in Indian MSMEs.

Consistent with established literature, Perceived Ease of Use (PEOU) significantly enhances Perceived Usefulness (PU) ($\beta=0.249$, $p<0.001$). Furthermore, both PEOU ($\beta=0.408$) and PU ($\beta=0.386$) are strong predictors of the Intention to Adopt (IA). This confirms that MSMEs are driven by tools that are both functionally beneficial and easy to operate.

The analysis revealed mixed results regarding external antecedents.

- **Competitive Pressure (CP) :-** The analysis showed a strong significant impact of CP on Perceived Ease of Use ($\beta=0.462$, $p<0.001$). This suggests that intense market competition may compel MSMEs to perceive technology as more accessible or necessary to master, effectively lowering the psychological barrier to entry.
- **Vendor Support (VS) :-** Vendor Support demonstrated a significant positive influence on Perceived Usefulness ($\beta=0.194$, $p=0.046$). This implies that when vendors provide adequate training and support, MSME managers perceive the tools as more capable

of delivering value.

- **Non-Significant Paths :-** Surprisingly, Employee Technical Skills (ETS) did not significantly influence Perceived Usefulness ($p=0.149$), and Financial Resources (FR) did not significantly influence Perceived Ease of Use ($p=0.713$). This indicates that simply having skills or money does not automatically translate into positive perceptions of the tool's utility or ease of use without other mediating factors.
- **Barriers in AI Adoption :-** The results indicate the effects of the structural barriers that condition the perception of MSMEs towards the use of AI. The perceived difficulty is added by technical constraints like the poor quality of the data, and ease of use becomes the focal point of adoption due to the complexity of system compatibility and integration (Kar et al 2021; Moradi and Dass 2022). The financial resources and skills of the employees did not exhibit any major outcomes even when they were present, which can be explained by organizational barriers, such as poor digital readiness and the lack of organised processes (Govori and Sejdija 2023; Campion et al 2022). The effects of skills on the perceived usefulness are also limited by human-resource constraints and resistance to technology (Hansen and Bogh 2021; Jadhav 2021). Additional risks such as data security, legal vagueness and inaccurate vendor support are external factors that make MSMEs cautious, which explains why vendor support is a relevant usefulness driver (Wei and Pardo 2022; Ade-Ibijola and Okonkwo 2023; Beltempo et al 2023). All these barriers moderate the effectiveness of TAM predictors and suggest that the adoption of AI is bound more by organizational and institutional

realities than technology itself.

6. Limitations and Future Research :- This study has limitations. First, the Standardized Root Mean Square Residual (SRMR) for the estimated model was 0.0872, which exceeds the conservative threshold of 0.08, suggesting need for additional interaction variables. Second, the structural paths analyzed for the external variables (CP, ETS, FR, VS) differed from the initial text hypotheses, suggesting that the model fit might be improved by realigning these variables.

7. Conclusion :- This research highlights that while the adoption of AI in digital marketing by Indian MSMEs is fundamentally driven by the ease of use and usefulness of the tools; external pressures play a complex role. Competitive pressure acts as a critical driver for overcoming complexity perceptions, while vendor support is essential for realizing the tool's utility. MSME owners should prioritize AI tools that offer strong vendor backing to ensure successful adoption.

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